

PROPERTIES OF DIALYSED HYDROUS ALUMINA HYDROSOLS PART I. p_H CHANGES DUE TO AGEING AND TITRATION WITH NEUTRAL SALTS.

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On ageing the p_H of hydrous alumina hydrosols slightly decreases and then becomes almost constant. Sols which contain free acids are more stable and give the same amount of chlorine on conductometric titration with different silver salts. Highly pure sols are less stable and the amount of chlorine obtained by conductometric titration with silver salts is in the order: sulphate < nitrate < acetate. The chlorine obtained by conductometric titration is less than the free or total chlorine content of the sols but in the case of less pure sols, this is almost equal to the free or the total chlorine content of them. Chlorine appears to be present in three different states. A part is free and the other bound. The former is made up of chlorine present in the intermicellary liquid and chlorine present in the mobile sheet of the double layer. As the purification of the sols by electro dialysis proceeds and the p_H rises, the portion of total chlorine associated with the colloidal particles, which remains 'bound' with the particles, increases. Neutral salts decrease the H^+ ion activity and increase the Cl^- ion activity of the sols. The order of effectiveness of the anions in both cases is chloride < sulphate < oxalate < ferrocyanide. A probable constitution of these sols has been suggested.

The electrochemical properties of colloidal hydrous alumina have been studied by several workers. Pauli and his co-workers (Adolf and Pauli, *Kolloid Z.*, 1921, 29, 281; Pauli and Valko, *Z physikal. Chem.*, 1926, 121, 164; Pauli and Schmidt, *ibid.*, 1927, 129, 199; Pauli and Muttone, *Kolloid Z.*, 1931, 87, 312; "Elektro chemie der Kolloide", 1929, p. 545) concluded from titration experiments with silver salts that the whole of the chlorine was in the reactive stage and considered these sols to be dispersions of basic salts having the composition $[mAl(OH)_3.nAlOCl. AlO^+] Cl^-$. Thomas and his co-workers (Thomas and Whitehead, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, 35, 27; Thomas and Tai, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 841; Thomas and Von Wicklen, *ibid.*, 1934, 56, 794; Whitehead and Clay, *ibid.*, 1934, 56, 1934; Whitehead, *Chem. Reviews*, 1937, 21, 113) considered that hydroxyl groups of highly basic salts of aluminium combine with one another to form 'ol' and ' μ ol' complexes. These complexes go on increasing till the aggregates formed by such linkages attain colloidal dimensions. According to them on the addition of an electrolyte its anions penetrate the complex and displace aquo or other anions present there. H^+ ions can also enter the complex and neutralise the hydroxo groups. The phenomena of ageing, the changes of p_H occurring on the addition of neutral salts etc. were interpreted on this basis. Weiser (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1920, 24, 505;

1931, 35, 1368; "Inorganic Colloid Chemistry", 1935, II, pp. 104-118) has pointed out that there was no direct evidence of the existence of a basic chloride and the assumption that alumina sols were basic complexes was not supported by X-ray analysis. According to him the interaction of alumina sols with electrolytes occurs in the electrical double layer surrounding the particles. The inner layer is supposed to contain Al^{+++} and H^+ ions and the outer layers Cl^- ions, a part of the Cl^- ions is rendered immobile being held by electrostatic forces. On the addition of electrolytes its anions are adsorbed in the outer layer and this is followed by an increased adsorption of cations. Multivalent ions would reduce the thickness of the double layer and so cause coagulation. During coagulation both anions and cations tend to be desorbed due to the diminution of the specific surface. Mattson (*Soil Sci.*, 1930, 30, 459) represented the composition of positively charged aluminium hydroxide as $(Al_2O_3)_x \cdot Al_2O_3^{++} + 2Cl^-$ and of negatively charged hydroxide as $Al(OH)_2(OH)^- + Na^+ \cdot Al^-$. Though it is generally assumed that NaOH forms the aluminate $NaAlO_2$, he considers that on the surface of the colloid and specially of soil colloids, a simple addition compound like the above is formed. Nikolsky and Paramonova (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1932, 159, 47) from a potentiometric study of the precipitation of aluminium salts with NaOH concluded that aluminium hydroxide in the colloidal state consisted of micelles on the surface of which there were $Al(OH)_3$ molecules and $Al(OH)_2^+$ and AlO_2^- groups formed respectively by the basic and acidic dissociation of the amphoteric hydroxide. In the outer layer there were the corresponding $(OH)^-$ and H^+ ions which could again be replaced by the cations and anions respectively of an added electrolyte. The basic dissociation would predominate below the isoelectric p_n and the acidic dissociation above it. The electrochemical properties of aluminium hydroxide sols have been studied previously in this laboratory (Mukherjee *et al.*, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 405; *Indian J. Agric. Sci.*, 1934, 4, 733; Mukherjee, *Kolloid Z.*, 1933, 63, 36; 1933, 65, 72). It has been observed that on dilution the p_n , specific conductivity and the chloride ion activity of the sol vary in a manner which is different from what would be expected of an electrolyte in true solution. Calculation of the specific conductivity, taking into account the amounts of electricity carried by the colloidal particles and by the oppositely charged ions, showed disagreement with the observed specific conductivities.

The sols used by these and other workers, however, had a fairly low p_n and high specific conductivity and probably contained free acids (or aluminium salts). The present investigation deals with a comparison of the properties of sols having different degrees of purity. Sols A and B have

low p_H and high specific conductivity and are similar to the sols used by other workers. Sols C, D, and E are of greater purity. Changes in p_H due to ageing and interaction with silver and potassium salts have been reported in this paper. The interaction of the sol with different electrolytes has been considered to occur in the electrical double layer surrounding the particles. The double layer has the following structure (*cf.* Mukherjee, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1921, 16, 103; *Phil. Mag.*, 1922, 44, 321). Its inner layer probably consists of primarily adsorbed Al^{+++} , AlO^+ and AlO_2^- ions. The relative amounts of these ions and the ratio of positive to negative charges depend on the p_H of the system. Hydroxyl, chloride or other anions and H^+ ions are present in the double layer partly in secondarily adsorbed *i.e.* bound condition and partly in a mobile, osmotically free condition. The relative amounts in these conditions again depend on the p_H and the composition of the intermicellary liquid.

According to this view chlorine, present in the sol, is likely to occur in different states. Part of the total chlorine, Cl_T , is present in association with the colloid particles, *i.e.* the micellar chlorine, Cl_M . The remaining part, the intermicellary chlorine, Cl_{IM} , is present in the intermicellary liquid. Micellary chlorine, Cl_M can be further subdivided into two fractions: one is osmotically active, denoted by $(Cl_M)_r$ and the other, osmotically inactive, denoted by $(Cl_M)_i$.

Hence

$$Cl_T = Cl_M + Cl_{IM} = (Cl_M)_i + (Cl_M)_r + Cl_{IM}$$

and total free chloride,

$$Cl_r = (Cl_M)_r + Cl_{IM} = Cl_T - (Cl_M)_i .$$

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Kahlbaum's pure $AlCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ was purified (Dennis, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1895, 9, 339) and hydrous alumina gel was precipitated from its solution in equilibrium water (sp. conductivity = 1.15×10^{-6} mho at 35°) by Merck's liquor ammonia diluted with equal volume of water. The gel was peptised completely by washing in a centrifuge and the resulting sols purified by ordinary dialysis. Sol A was dialysed for three weeks and sol B for a period extending over $1\frac{1}{2}$ months. In the case of sols C, D and E, further purification has been effected by electrodialysis after dialysis lasting for 2 to 3 weeks. The hydrous alumina contained adsorbed ammonia which was not easily removed by washing in the centrifuge and was only slowly removed during dialysis. On prolonged electrodialysis most of the alumina was precipitated in flocks and dilute sols were obtained.

A Tinsley vernier potentiometer in conjunction with a Hartmann and Braun galvanometer (type 159) was used for measuring the e.m.f. The p_H was measured by the hydrogen electrode against normal calomel electrode* using saturated KCl in the bridge. The hydrogen gas was obtained by the electrolysis of caustic soda solution in a U-tube with platinum electrodes. The gas was purified by passing it through concentrated sulphuric acid, soda lime, a tube containing copper gauze heated in an electric furnace (400°) and finally through soda lime and conductivity water. The Cl^- ion activity was measured with Ag-AgCl electrode (Noyes and Ellis, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 39, 2532) in conjunction with another Ag-AgCl electrode placed in 0.1N-KCl solution using saturated NH_4NO_3 in the bridge. The potentiometric and conductometric titrations were carried out in pyrex glass titration cells provided with air-tight ground glass joints (*Indian J. Agric. Sci.*, 1936, 6, 519) which allowed simultaneous measurement of chloride and hydrogen ion activities. The assembly for the measurement of specific conductivity consisted of an oscillator working at 500 and 1000 cycles per second, a non-inductive resistance box and a marble drum bridge. A condenser of variable capacity was connected in parallel with the resistance box in order to balance the capacity of the cell. The alumina content was estimated as Al_2O_3 . Total chlorine was estimated by potentiometric titration with silver salts after solution of the sol in nitric acid by Ag-AgCl electrodes. A water thermostat covered with a layer of oil has been used at $35 \pm 0.05^\circ$.

For sols having very low hydrogen and chloride ion activities and low specific conductivities, the measurement of the e.m.f. is attended with various difficulties. Electrical leakages often prove very troublesome; to obviate this the metal cover of the experimental table, the lead outer covers of the electrical connections and all exposed terminals etc. were earth connected. The temperature of the room was kept a little higher than the surroundings in order that moisture may not condense on the terminals. To eliminate diffusion of KCl from the beaker containing saturated KCl, into the cell, the U-tube connecting the latter with the beaker was fitted with a stop-cock. Before the measurements the U-tube was taken out and the piston of the stop-cock rinsed with KCl and replaced. The tube was then washed thoroughly with water, filled with the sol and inserted into its position in the cell with the stop-cock closed. The junction potential was eliminated as usual by interposing a saturated KCl bridge. It is well known, however, that complete elimination of the junction potential is not effected thereby. The results obtained in this laboratory with some

* The e.m.f. of N-calomel electrode was taken as 0.2823 volt at 35° (Sørensen and Linderstrøm Lang, *Compt. rend. Lab. Carlsberg*, 1924, 25).

solutions of HCl (Mitra, *Indian J. Agric. Sci.*, 1940, 10, 318) illustrate the reliability of the technique and of the electrodes used in these measurements. Using this technique and following the method used by the author in the case of stearic acid sols (Mukherjee and Datta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 563), the reproducibility of the p_n measurements as carried out on different days was fairly satisfactory, the limits of reproducibility being 0·1 or p_n unit (Table II).

In order to test the accuracy of Ag/AgCl electrode measurements, several Ag/AgCl electrodes were prepared. The chloride ion activities of HCl at two dilutions were measured with these electrodes and care was taken to make the system free from air. The E.M.F. of the concentration cell was reproducible within 0·1 millivolt. The following data show the agreement between the observed and the calculated E.M.F.

Cell : $\overset{\vee}{\text{Ag}}/\text{AgCl}/0\cdot001N\text{-KCl}/\text{saturated NH}_4\text{NO}_3/0\cdot01N\text{-KCl}/\text{Ag}/\text{Ag}\bar{\text{Cl}}$
 (Observed E.M.F. = 0·0610 volt at 35°.)

FIG. 1.

The E.M.F. calculated from the activity coefficients given by Randall and Young ("Thermodynamics", 1923) is 0·0594 volt at 25°. The E.M.F. of the electrodes was also sufficiently reproducible. The titrations were

repeated in some cases to check the reproducibility. The agreement among the duplicated curves was fairly satisfactory (Fig. 1).

Composition of Sols.

TABLE I.

Sol	Alumina content in g. moles per litre.	Al ⁺⁺⁺ ion.	Free Cl ⁻ ion (Cl _r) in g. moles per litre.	Total Cl (Cl _t) in g. moles per litre.	NH ₃ .	p _H .	Sp. condy. (mho).
A	1.37 × 10 ⁻³	Nil	13.18 × 10 ⁻³	13.75 × 10 ⁻³	Nil	4.73	19.3 × 10 ⁻⁴
B	0.78	,	7.65	9.78	"	5.60	15.60
C	1.25	"	6.30	8.10	"	6.42	8.80
D	1.30	"	3.40	8.00	"	6.51	7.06
E	0.62	,	2.25	6.04	"	6.70	5.20

None of these sols contains either any free aluminium ions or ammonia as shown by ultrafiltrate test of the sol with 8-oxyquinoline or Nessler's reagent. With the progress of purification, the specific conductivity and the hydrogen and chloride ion activities of the sol appreciably decrease. The p_H of the sols C, D and E is nearly neutral and the specific conductivity is of the order of the equilibrium water used. Sols A and B, however, are less pure than the other two. From columns 4 and 5 (Table I) it is apparent that the whole of the chlorine is not osmotically active (free).

p_H Changes due to Ageing.

Hydrous alumina hydrosols have been observed to undergo with time changes in p_H. Thomas and Whitehead (*loc. cit.*) found an increase in p_H of aluminium oxychloride hydrosols due to ageing at 20°. In 54 days the p_H increased from 4.54 to 4.75 and from 4.56 to 5.4 for two different sols. Thomas and Tai (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 841) working with aluminium oxyiodide sols at 90° obtained a decrease in p_H after ten days but on further ageing the p_H increased. But Weiser (*loc. cit.*) using three sols observed uniformly a decrease of 0.39 to 0.13 p_H units in about 3 months. Pugh (*Soil Sci.*, 1934, 37, 403) prepared a sol from isoelectric precipitates and observed that the p_H changed from 7.31 to 4.57 in 40 day and the p_H did not remain constant thereafter. On the other hand, B. Majumdar (*unpublished work*) in this laboratory found that neglecting some erratic variations the p_H remained almost constant after some time.

TABLE II.
 p_n Changes on ageing.

Sol A.		Sol C.		Sol D.	
Date.	p_n .	Date.	p_n .	Date.	p_n .
4-8-38	5'26	12-11-38	6'93	19-9-39	7'08
6-8-38	5'06	13-11-38	6'90	28-9-39	7'02
10-8-38	4'95	26-11-38	6'88	5-10-39	7'00
11-8-38	4'82	23-12-38	6'42	30-11-39	6'62
9-2-39	4'75	27-12-38	6'42	29-11-39	6'51
22-4-39	4'75	4-1-39	6'42	2-12-39	6'51
		15-1-39	6'43	7-12-39	6'51

It will be found that the p_n of all these sols decreased gradually and ultimately reached practically constant values. While it is simpler to ascribe this decrease in p_n to the slow hydrolysis of the adsorbed aluminium salts present on the surface of the particles, Thomas and Whitehead (*loc. cit.*) explained the increase observed by them in terms of their colation and oxolation theories according to which H^+ ions from the solution enter the sol

complex and neutralise the hydroxo groups. Aluminium hydroxide sols probably contain hydroxo groups in their micelles (discussed later) but whether H^+ ions do or do not enter the complex colloidal micelle during ageing in the manner suggested is an open question. An examination of the data in Table I of their paper shows that sols probably contained ammonia which was slowly desorbed and neutralised by hydrogen ions and the p_H increased in consequence. Their sol B containing the largest amount of ammonia showed the largest p_H increase. Weiser (*loc. cit.*) ascribed the decrease in p_H observed by him to the liberation of stabilising hydrogen ions from the colloidal micelles due to coalescence with age but the slow hydrolysis of adsorbed aluminium chloride, which was used by him for peptisation, is a contributory factor. The surprisingly large decrease in p_H observed by Pugh (*loc. cit.*) is very probably the result of the hydrolysis of large amounts of aluminium chloride likely to be present under the conditions of preparation of the sol.

FIG. 4.
Hydrous alumina sol E—Ag salt titration.

PROPERTIES OF DIALYSED HYDROUS ALUMINA HYDROSOLS

Titration with Silver Salts.

Pauli and Schmidt (*loc. cit.*) and later Thomas and Tai (*loc. cit.*) found that conductometric titration of aluminium hydroxide sols with different silver salts gives a constant amount of chlorine which is identical with the total amount obtained by dissolving the colloid in nitric acid. Raychaudhury, Sen and Chatterjee (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 13) obtained a greater value on titration with silver acetate than silver nitrate.

Sols A, B, C, D and E have been titrated conductometrically and the sol D, both conductometrically and potentiometrically, with silver acetate, nitrate and sulphate. Total chlorine in the sols has been determined by potentiometric titration. The titration curves for sols A, B, D and E only are shown in Figs. 1-4. The amounts of chlorine obtained from the inflexion points of these curves and also from those not shown are given in Table III.

TABLE III.

Reagent		Amount of chlorine* (g. moles per litre).	Reagent		Amount of chlorine* (g. moles per litre).
Vol. reqd. at the break.	Strength.		Vol. reqd. at the break.	Strength	
Sol A (10 c.c.)					
0'36 c.c. of AgNO ₃	0'011 N	13'04 × 10 ⁻³	0'205 c.c. of AgNO ₃	0'00098 N	0'79
" "	"	13'04	0'180 c.c. of Ag ₂ SO ₄	0'00097 N	0'69
0'315 c.c. of Ag-acetate	0'0126 N	13'09			0'80 †
		13'75**			0'69 †
Sol B (50 c.c.)					
0'038 c.c. of AgNO ₃	0'0066 N	0'50	Sol E (50 c.c.)		
0'026 " "	0'01 N	0'51	0'014 c.c. of AgNO ₃	0'01 N	0'28
" " Ag ₂ SO ₄	0'01 N	0'51	0'225 " " "	0'00066 N	0'29
0'039 " Ag acetate	0'0065 N	0'51	0'075 " " Ag ₂ SO ₄	0'00066 N	0'10
0'026 " "	0'0098 N	0'51	0'0525 " " "	0'001 N	0'1
		9'78**	0'016 " " Ag acetate	0'0098 N	0'31
Sol C (30 c.c.)					
0'09 c.c. of AgNO ₃	0'0011 N	0'32	0'026 " " " "	0'0065 N	0'33
0'03 c.c. of Ag-acetate	0'0034 N	0'33			6'04**
		8'2**			

* Estimated by conductometric titration except where stated otherwise.

** Total chlorine by pot. titration with AgNO₃.

† Chlorine by pot. titration of ultrafiltrate with Ag NO₃

‡ Do. by " " of sol " "

Conductometric titration of sol A with the acetate and the nitrate gives an amount of chlorine, Cl_C which is very nearly equal to the free chlorine, Cl_F , calculated from the E.M.F. of the Ag-AgCl electrode but is somewhat smaller than Cl_T obtained by analysis. In the case of sols B, C, D and E, however, Cl_C is much smaller than Cl_T and even Cl_F . Cl_C is definitely greater than the chlorine found in the ultrafiltrate of the sol (*cf.* Sol D, Fig. 5). Titration with different silver salts gives values in the order: sulphate < nitrate < acetate. The percentages of $(Cl_M)_B$, $(Cl_M)_F$, Cl_M in terms of Cl_T are given in Table IV.

TABLE IV.

Sol.	Cl_T expressed	Cl_C in g. moles. per litre.	Cl_M per litre.	Cl_M expressed in	$(Cl_M)_F$	$(Cl_M)_B$ % Cl_T .
A	13.75×10^{-4}	13.18×10^{-4}	...	...	...	4.1
B	9.78	7.65	..	...	...	20.0
C	8.2	6.3	...	...	...	23.1
D	8.0	3.2	0.69×10^{-3}	92.0	21.5	60.0
E	6.04	2.25	...	...	...	62.7

The amount of the osmotically inactive chlorine $(Cl_M)_B$ in the different sols is in the order: sol E > sol D > sol C > sol B > sol A. The H^+ ion concentrations and specific conductivities of the sols are in the reverse order.

Titration with Neutral Solution of Potassium Salts

Thomas and Whitehead (*loc. cit.*) and Thomas and Tai (*loc. cit.*) observed an increase of the p_H of hydrous alumina sols on titration with potassium salts; with the oxalate or acetate the p_H passed through a maximum. They attributed the rise in p_H to the replacement of hydroxo groups of the complex by anions, and considered that the oxalate was more effective because of its greater 'penetrating power'. The subsequent decrease was explained as arising out of "salt effects." The simultaneous displacement of chloride ions by the salt solutions has not been recorded in the above paper. Weiser (*loc. cit.*) found that Cl^- ions were displaced. The rise in the p'' of the sol obtained on the addition of potassium oxalate was attributed to the slight alkalinity of the $K_2C_2O_4$ solutions.

Changes in the hydrogen and chloride ion activities of sol D consequent on the addition of neutral* normal solutions of KCl, K₂SO₄, K₂C₂O₄ and K₄Fe(CN)₆ have been shown in Fig. 5. The neutral salts decrease the

FIG. 5.

activity of hydrogen ions and increase that of the chloride ions to a marked degree. The change is at first rapid, then more slow and ultimately almost constant values are reached. The order of effectiveness of anion in raising the p_H and in decreasing the p_{Cl} is the same, namely chloride

* The p_H of the salt solutions was adjusted to 7.0, on adding small amounts of acid or alkali. This did not materially alter the concentration of the anion in the solution.

< sulphate < oxalate < ferrocyanide. The final p_H in all cases is on the alkaline side and for the oxalate and the ferrocyanide it rises to about 8.75. A comparison with the rise in p_H on adding these salts to water containing a trace of HCl to bring the p_H near about that of the sol (Fig. 5) shows that the increment in p_H is not due to the alkalinity of the salt solution as suggested by Weiser (*loc. cit.*) but should be ascribed to the displacement of OH ions by the anions.

In the titration with ferrocyanide, the Ag/AgCl electrode appears to have been poisoned as the displaced chlorine is greater than the total concentration of chlorine in the sol.

Structure of the Micelles.

The views of Pauli and Valko (*loc. cit.*), Thomas and Whitehead (*loc. cit.*) and of Weiser (*loc. cit.*) regarding the micellar structure of hydrous alumina sols have been fully described by Weiser ("Inorganic Colloid Chemistry", Vol. II, 1935). The results described above admit of a simple explanation if the following structure is ascribed for the micelles :

The core of the micelle has the composition xAl_2O_3, yH_2O . The isoelectric p_H is 8.2 for alumina precipitated from the chloride (Mattson, *Soil Sci.*, 1930, 30, 459). In the titrations of aluminium salts with alkalis, precipitation of alumina begins at about p_H 3.5 and is complete at p_H about 6.8. Above this p_H the precipitated alumina dissolves in the alkali and solution is complete at about p_H 10.9 with the formation of $NaAlO_2$, (Further discussed in Part II of this series ; also Britton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 2120; Hildebrand, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 35, 864; Blum, *ibid.*, 1913, 35, 1499). The dissociation constant of aluminic acid $HAlO_2$ can be taken to be of the order of 10^{-10} *. It is reasonable to assume that during the precipitation of hydrous alumina by alkalis from aluminium salts, in the acid region the solution will contain Al^{+++} , H^+ and probably AlO^+ ions. The latter is probably formed near about p_H 6 and occurs for the case in which chloride ions are adsorbed on the surface near this region perhaps to form $AlOCl$ (*Indian J. Agric. Sci.*, 1934, 4, 733). In the alkaline region, on the other hand, the system will contain OH^- and AlO_2^- ions. In the intermediate range of p_H , all these positive and negative ions will be simultaneously present, their relative proportion being determined by the

* Regarding the dissociation constant of aluminic acid there is some controversy (*cf* Blum, *loc. cit.*; Mahin, Ingraham and Stewart, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 35, 30 ; Slade, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1912, 77, 457).

prevailing p_n . Hydrus alumina during precipitation therefore will contain on its surface a primarily adsorbed layer of ions (Mukherjee, *loc. cit.*) both positive and negative ions, their relative numbers depending on the p_n of the sol. If this p_n is low, the ratio of primarily adsorbed positive to negative ions will be large or practically infinite and the particles will be positively charged. On the other hand, if the p_n is high, this ratio will be small or practically zero and the particles will be negatively charged. The positive ions on the surface, Al^{+++} or AlO^+ , will draw an equivalent number of negatively charged ions, OH^- , Cl^- , near them some of which will be secondarily adsorbed neutralising a portion of the positive charge. The rest of the balancing negatively charged ions balancing the free positive charge will be in the diffuse or mobile sheet of the double layer. A similar relation holds for the negatively charged ions AlO_2^- on the surface, the balancing ions in this case being cations *e.g.*, H^+ ions and the cations of the added base. The proposed structure is diagrammatically represented in Fig. 6.

FIG. 6.

[The ratio of +ve to -ve primarily adsorbed ions depends on p_n].

DISCUSSION.

Titration with Silver Salts.—The silver salts first react with the free chloride in the intermicellary liquid and then with the mobile and bound chloride ions of the double layer. The chlorine of the primarily adsorbed layer and that present as $AlOCl$ will be the last to react. The extent to which the reaction will proceed appears to be conditioned by the stability of the sol. The silver salts tend to coagulate the sol. If the sol is not sufficiently stable, coagulation may set in before the chlorine has completely

reacted with the silver salt and a considerable part may be blocked within the coagulum and thus left unreacted upon. This accounts for the much smaller Cl_c than Cl_r or Cl_t of sols B, C, D and E. For sol A, Cl_c is equal to Cl_r and very nearly equal to Cl_t . This sol unlike others has a definitely acid reaction and the p_n is low enough to ensure the presence of Al^{+++} and AlO^+ ions on the surface as a primarily adsorbed layer. That coagulation plays a part in the estimation of the chlorine by conductometric titrations is indicated by the fact that the Cl_c values obtained with different silver salts are in the order $SO_4' < NO_3' < Ac'$. The relative effects of these anions on the coagulation of positively charged hydrous alumina sols are also in this order.

In the titration with salts or acids, the p_n of the sols is in the alkaline and acidic regions respectively and hydrous alumina sols are known to be stable in acidic or alkaline regions, whereas in the titration with silver salts, the p_n remains near about the neutral region where it is the least stable. It can therefore be understood why in the titration with silver salts the sols get coagulated more quickly and chlorine obtained is less and follows the order that is found. It is also possible that in the initial stages sulphate displaces more chlorine and more $AgCl$ is formed than either with the nitrate or acetate. The $AgCl$ may thus form a greater coating on the colloid particles and thus the particles escape reaction and a smaller amount of chlorine reacts with the sulphate.

Pauli and Schmidt (*loc. cit.*) have interpreted their results to mean that the whole of the chlorine is in the reactive state. But it appears from the low p_n value (4.51) of their sols, that they were similar to, but more stable than sol A. It does not appear difficult therefore to see why these authors obtained the same total amount of chlorine by conductometric titration with different silver salts.

Titration with Potassium Salts.—The change in p_n and p_{el} with the addition of K salts is significant. It shows simultaneous presence of OH^- and Cl^- ions in the double layer and they are both displaced by the anions of the salt solutions. The observed changes can be explained as follows:

On the addition of a salt, its anions enter into the diffuse or mobile layer of ions and are adsorbed secondarily to an extent depending on the condition. As a result of their penetration into the double layer, they displace OH^- and Cl^- ions into solution. The K^+ ions are not likely to be secondarily adsorbed to any large extent but they should be capable of displacing H^+ ions into solution. Two opposite forces have to be thus

taken into consideration so far as the p_H changes are concerned. These are the adsorption of anions which tend to increase the p_H and the adsorption of K^+ ions which tend to lower the p_H . Their relative magnitude depends again on the condition in the double layer. The amount of displacement of the different ions at any instant will depend on the ratio of positive to negative ions in the double layer at that instant. This ratio as has already been stated, depends on the p_H of the system. In the pure sol there is a preponderance of positive charges over negative charges. In the initial stages of the titration, the relative effect of the anions will therefore be greater than that of K^+ ions. The net effect will result in an increase in p_H . As the p_H increases, the ratio of positive to negative charges in the primarily adsorbed layer of ions decreases and the adsorption of K^+ ions and consequently the displacement of H^+ ions increases. In the later stages of the titration, the two opposing forces will balance and the p_H will remain constant. The anions of the added salt displacing Cl^- ions from the double layer into the intermicellar liquid increases the chloride ion activity of the sol.

C O N C L U S I O N .

Highly purified hydrous alumina hydrosols of high p_H and low specific conductivity (sols C, D and E) have been prepared by peptisation of hydrous alumina precipitated from purified aluminium chloride and pure ammonia and purified by dialysis and electro-dialysis. Their electrochemical properties have been studied and compared with sols of lower p_H and higher specific conductivity prepared by the same method but purified only by ordinary dialysis (sols A and B).

On ageing, the p_H of hydrous alumina sols slightly decreases and then becomes almost constant.

In sols A and B same amount of chlorine is obtained by conductometric titration with different silver salts and this for sol A is almost equal to the total chlorine concentration of the sol. Conductometric and potentiometric titrations of sols C, D and E, however with different silver salts give an amount of chlorine which is much smaller than either the free or the total chlorine content of them. Further interesting is the observation that in conductometric titrations, sulphate gives a smaller amount of chlorine than nitrate and nitrate smaller than acetate.

The difference between the total chlorine and that contained in the ultrafiltrate represents the amount of chlorine that is present in association with the colloid particles of which part is free and part is bound.

As the sols become more and more pure, the percentage of bound chlorine becomes greater. Neutral salts decrease the H^+ ion activity and increase the Cl^- ion activity of the sols. The order of effectiveness of the anions in both cases is chloride < sulphate < oxalate < ferrocyanide.

A probable constitution of these sols has been suggested.

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